

Results report

Strengthening the Conceptual and Pedagogical Capacities of Teachers in Tambogrande, to Prevent and Address Gender-Based Violence in the Educational Environment

Authors:

Paula Skye Tallman
Lucia López Flórez
Marixa Bobadilla

The project **“Strengthening the Conceptual and Pedagogical Capacities of Teachers in Tambogrande, to Prevent and Address Gender-Based Violence in the Educational Environment”** was carried out between July and August 2025. The intervention was facilitated with 38 teachers from the Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48, and implemented by Loyola University Chicago (USA), the Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48 in Tambogrande. The objective of the intervention was to strengthen the conceptual and pedagogical capacities of the teaching staff to promote gender equality and to recognize, prevent, and address GBV within the educational environment. In this context, this was through promoting teaching practices that foster respectful, equitable, and discrimination-free relationships and interactions. To achieve this, the initiative delivered training workshops which included information and activities focused on:

Understanding gender dynamics in order to identify sexist attitudes or practices within teaching and/or school environments.

Designing pedagogical strategies that help break cycles of discrimination and contribute to forming a more empathetic, just, and free generation.

- Becoming familiar with instruments and mechanisms that support recognizing, reporting, and addressing cases of violence from both
- community and educational settings.

This report presents the results of the process carried out, the progress achieved in capacity building, the emerging lessons learned, and the recommendations for sustainability. It is also framed within the Sustainable Development Goals, primarily SDG 5 (gender equality), as well as SDG 4 (quality education) and SDG 17 (partnerships for the goals), which guided the design and implementation of this initiative.

The initiative was implemented in the Tambogrande district of Piura. In this context, the normalization of machista practices and the reproduction of gender stereotypes continue to limit the opportunities of girls, adolescents, and women (Archdeacon et al., 2024). Additionally, a study conducted by the same institution highlights deeply rooted beliefs that perpetuate gendered inequalities and restrict women's opportunities.

This proposal originates from the research study "Water Insecurity and Gender-Based Violence: Exploring Links and Pathways for Prevention. A Comparative Study of Indonesian and Peruvian Women", funded by the British Academy and implemented between 2020 and 2023 by the Pontifical Catholic University of Peru (PUCP). The study analyzed the link between water insecurity and gender-based violence on the left bank of Tambogrande, Piura, and revealed that one of the most effective prevention strategies—according to local stakeholders—was to strengthen teachers' capacities through sustained training processes.

Building on these findings, in 2023, a first intervention was carried out in partnership with the Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48, targeting early childhood education teachers. This experience, funded by the PUCP Social Responsibility Fund (RSU-PUCP), included theoretical/practical workshops on mainstreaming the gender approach in the curriculum and critical analysis of educational materials. Its implementation demonstrated the need to expand these processes to other educational levels and actors, as well as to involve families.

In line with this, in 2024 workshops were conducted with 3rd-year secondary school students, focusing on the deconstruction of gender stereotypes, reflection on machista culture, and the promotion of life projects free from gender-based limitations.

These antecedents underpin the current intervention, which seeks to deepen the work already initiated. After working with students, the intervention has now shifted its focus to primary and secondary school teachers, with the aim of expanding their understanding of gender-based violence (GBV) and providing them with pedagogical tools to address it effectively within the educational environment.

DEVELOPMENT OF WORKSHOPS

The project was implemented between July 17 and August 12, 2025, through six theoretical-practical workshops delivered to 18 primary school teachers and 20 secondary school teachers. The sessions were held from 2:30 p.m. to 4:30 p.m. and were complemented by an extended session on August 7.

Below is a detailed description of the workshops carried out:

Session	Date	Specific objective
Session 1. Conceptual framework: sex, gender, and the sexual division of labor	July 17, 2025	Strengthen teachers' critical understanding of the conceptual framework of sex, gender, and the sexual division of labor.
Session 2. Gender stereotypes and the construction of new masculinities	August 7, 2025	Promote critical reflection on gender stereotypes and traditional constructions of masculinity, fostering pedagogical approaches that encourage respectful and responsible masculinities.
Session 3. Differentiated impacts of GBV	August 7, 2025	Raise awareness and train teachers to identify, prevent, and address GBV, understanding its emotional, social, and academic impacts on students.
Session 4. Roadmap for addressing school violence related to GBV	August 7, 2025	Strengthen capacities for the rigorous and empathetic application of institutional procedures and protocols in cases of school violence.
Session 5. Mainstreaming gender, human rights, and intercultural approaches	August 7, 2025	Raise awareness among teachers on how to mainstream gender, human rights, and intercultural approaches into their pedagogical practice, promoting respect, dignity, and diversity.

Session	Date	Specific objective
Session 6. Development of management tools with a human rights approach	August 12, 2025	Develop management documents and pedagogical proposals using gender equality, human rights, and intercultural approaches aimed at transforming inequalities in the school environment.

METHODOLOGY

The intervention consisted of six theoretical-practical sessions delivered through participatory and dynamic workshops involving the teachers. The workshops were facilitated by Marixa Bobadilla, a licensed educator with a Master's degree in Education Sciences Didactics, and specialized training in gender and public policy, the prevention of GBV in schools, human rights, citizenship, and sexual education. The facilitator has extensive experience in educational projects with a gender approach in Piura and Cajamarca.

From an operational standpoint, the Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48 oversaw the local logistics, which included the recruitment of participating teachers, internal coordination, and the provision of adequate spaces for the workshops. This collaborative work ensured an implementation that was timely and grounded in the educational reality of the territory.

Methodological approach

The workshops were designed sequentially and progressively, linking conceptual development with critical reflection and pedagogical application. They combined conceptual presentations, case analyses, group dynamics, and reflective activities. Each session addressed one of the initiative's specific objectives and aimed to strengthen key teaching competencies for building safe, equitable, and violence-free school environments.

METHODOLOGY

Data collection

To assess the changes produced by the training process, pre- and post-workshop surveys were administered to the teachers. In total, 30 teachers responded to both instruments, which enabled comparative analysis. The surveys included items based on the UN Women Study of Attitudes on Gender Equality (2021), which contains 23 five-point Likert scale questions designed to assess perceptions of gender roles, gender stereotypes, and GBV. Three open-ended qualitative questions were added to this instrument to capture teachers' perceived preparedness to address situations of GBV.

Qualitative analysis

Open-ended responses were analyzed using inductive thematic analysis (Woo, O'Boyle & Spector, 2017). The process was carried out by senior members of the team, who coded the responses and engaged in internal discussions to ensure consistency and reliability in the interpretation of the data.

Quantitative analysis

Quantitative data were processed using STATA 15.0. To evaluate significant changes between pre- and post-intervention measurements, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test for paired samples was applied, considering results with $p < 0.05$ as statistically significant.

Funding

The project was funded by Loyola University Chicago and implemented by Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48.

ACHIEVEMENTS AND CHALLENGES BY SESSION

This section systematizes the main achievements and challenges identified during the implementation of the six workshops aimed at teachers. The information is drawn from the facilitator's observations and the analysis of the group dynamics carried out in each session. Its organization makes it possible to identify pedagogical, conceptual, and attitudinal advances, as well as the operational and methodological challenges that influenced the training process. This comprehensive reading helps guide future interventions and strengthen the continuity of work with the teaching staff.

Topics	Achievements	Challenges
Session 1. Conceptual framework: sex, gender, and the sexual division of labor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They understood the difference between natural characteristics (sex) and learned behaviors (gender) • They recognized that the socialization process begins in the family, continues at school, and is reinforced by society. 	Fatigue affected the engagement of a group of teachers. It was necessary to adjust the planned activity structure to maintain participation.
Session 2. Gender stereotypes and the construction of new masculinities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They reflected on gender stereotypes and hegemonic masculinity. • They identified expressions of violence among men linked to economic power, physical appearance, or social status. • They recognized structural barriers faced by women, such as interrupted studies or the exclusive burden of household care. 	No challenges were reported in this session.
Session 3. Differentiated impacts of GBV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They identified the importance of understanding the response pathways for GBV cases within the school and the community. • They experienced the frustration felt by victims when institutions do not respond on time. 	No challenges were reported in this session.

Topic	Achievements	Challenges
<p>Session 4. Roadmap for addressing school violence related to GBV</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They understood the importance of complying with the coexistence protocols contained in Annex No. 3 of the Guidelines for School Coexistence Management (D.S. 004-2018-MINEDU), with emphasis on Protocol 06 on violence perpetrated by school staff against students. • They understood the responsibility of teachers to accompany victims and ensure the reporting of any act of violence, even if it occurs outside the school. • They recognized the usefulness of Law 30364 and resources such as CEMs and the 100 Hotline. • They analyzed Protocols 1 to 5 in groups, identifying responsibilities of the management team and the coexistence committee. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The presence of the CEM modified the planned work sequence. • Conceptual gaps were identified in group presentations, and participants committed to addressing them in the following session.
<p>Session 5. Mainstreaming gender, human rights, and interculturality</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They reflected on the Ministry of Education’s transversal approaches. • They produced a metacognition chart highlighting the need to strengthen knowledge of action protocols within the school community. 	<p>Limited time prevented deeper discussion on the importance of gender, human rights, and intercultural approaches.</p>
<p>Session 6. Building institutional management tools with a human-rights approach</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They worked in groups on the importance of gender equality and rights-based approaches in pedagogical and institutional management. • They understood the difference between “mainstreaming” and “crossing” approaches in daily curricular practice. • They represented four types of GBV (physical, psychological, sexual, and patrimonial/economic) through short dramatizations, enabling comparative reflection. • The management team demonstrated conceptual mastery of the approaches, reflected in the Institutional Educational Project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pending conceptual questions about types of GBV from previous sessions which were addressed in this session. • Not all groups were able to present their work due to physical space limitations.

The development of the workshops demonstrated a progressive process of awareness-raising, critical reflection, and conceptual understanding among the teaching staff. Teachers were able to identify the difference between sex and gender, recognize normalized practices of hegemonic masculinity, and understand the role of the school in preventing violence.

A significant achievement was the increased recognition of current regulations—including Law 30364, the school coexistence system, and Annex No. 3 of the MINEDU protocols, particularly Protocol 6 regarding cases of violence committed by school personnel—as well as the identification of referral pathways such as the Women’s Emergency Centers (CEM) and the 100 Hotline. Practical activities, especially the sociodramas, facilitated a deeper understanding of the emotional and pedagogical implications of GBV in the school environment.

Among the most recurrent challenges were the accumulated fatigue of teachers, who attended the workshops after their workday, and the warm climate of the area, which affected concentration during long sessions. Conceptual gaps were also identified regarding transversal approaches and the application of response protocols, requiring pauses to reinforce content. In some sessions, the participation of external actors (such as the CEM) required adjustments to the timing and planned development of activities.

Overall, the experience reflected a sustained process of awareness-raising and teacher engagement, with significant progress in understanding GBV and the institutional responsibility for its prevention and response.

QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

Most teachers expressed favorable views toward gender equality prior to the intervention.

The quantitative survey (UN Women, 2019), administered before and after the programming, provides a window into understanding the beliefs of the teachers on issues related to gender equality at baseline and whether the programming influenced these beliefs.

Briefly, we found that the majority of teachers expressed opinions supporting gender equality before the programming began. For example, the majority of participants disagreed with statements such as:

- “A man’s job is to earn money; a woman’s job is to look after the house and the family”
- “For the same job, men should be paid more than women”
- “It is natural for men to earn more than women, as they should be the main providers”
- “A woman should not earn more than her husband”

Participants also disagreed with statements about unequal occupational and educational opportunities such as”

- “Is it more important for a boy to get a university education than a girl”
- “Women should work less and devote more time to caring for their families”
- “When jobs are scarce, men should have more right to a job than women”

Teachers also made it clear that they support women’s reproductive choices and the right to live lives free of violence agreeing with statements such as:

- “A woman should be free to refuse sex with her husband / partner”
- “It is important for women to have access to family planning”
- “Women should be free to make choices regarding marriage - if they marry at all as well as when and whom they marry.”

Additionally, the majority of participants disagreed with the statement that, “There are acceptable circumstances for someone to hit their spouse or partner”.

There were a few questions with quantitatively significant changes in beliefs after the programming.

For example, before the programming, the teachers were mixed on whether they agreed or disagreed on the statement, “When a mother works for pay, the children suffer”. After the programming, there was a significant increase in the number of participants disagreeing with this statement.

Participants also had mixed responses in regard to the statement, that “Women call attention to themselves based on how they dress” and that “It is appropriate for men to discuss a female colleague’s appearance at work”. In both cases, participants also moved toward disagreement after the programming.

Finally, teachers were split in their views on the statements, “In the media in my area/community (television, radio, others), men are usually represented in traditional male roles: breadwinners, leaders” and “Having a paid job is the best way for a woman to be an independent person”. These divisions remained after the programming.

To summarize, the teachers who participated in the programming began with strong beliefs in gender equality, as reflected in their opinions on gender roles, stereotypes, and expectations across men and women. The quantitative data revealed some shifts toward greater alignment with support for women’s rights after the programming – particularly in regard to beliefs about respecting women’s choices with how they dress and whether it is appropriate to comment on appearances at work. Future analyses will compare the results of students in 2024, with the results from teachers presented here, to assess how students and teachers differed in their baseline beliefs and in their responses to the programming.

QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Perception of safety and ability to detect cases of GBV

The qualitative questions applied before and after the intervention made it possible to identify teachers' knowledge regarding the identification of gender-based violence (GBV) in the educational setting, as well as their awareness of institutional and state policies for its response and follow-up.

At the outset, most teachers did not explicitly express high levels of confidence in their ability to detect cases of GBV, although they did identify key signs of students experiencing violence – such as behavioral, emotional, physical, and social changes—that could alert the teachers to problems. Some teachers reported feeling confident or relatively capable of detecting such cases, mainly due to their classroom experience. However, a significant group expressed doubts about their capacity, pointing to a lack of specialized training and the difficulty of distinguishing clear indicators: “I am not one hundred percent sure, but some traits may include...” (M12) and “I am not a specialist... but I recognize some signs such as changes in behavior in the classroom and in interactions with peers” (M9).

After the intervention, this trend changed considerably, with more teachers reporting feeling confident or very confident in their ability to identify signs of GBV. One participant stated: “I feel very confident in detecting and knowing how to act in these situations; the signs include changes in attitude and behavior, reduced participation, and isolation” (M11), while another teacher added: “I feel capable of listening and detecting any sign of violence, as well as acting immediately: poor academic performance, shyness, limited interaction with boys in the case of girls and vice versa, and fear of speaking” (F4).

Likewise, both before and after the intervention, most teachers reported observing behavioral, emotional, physical, and social changes that could signal a situation of violence

Regarding behavior, they reported identifying changes in students' attitudes, evidenced by more aggressive or defiant behaviors, mood swings, decreased participation, or changes in personality. As one teacher explains: "Changes in students' behavior: aggressive, violent behaviors, among others, and isolation within the group" (F2). Within this pattern, isolation, withdrawal, shyness, and avoidance of interactions stand out. Within this pattern, isolation, withdrawal, shyness, and avoidance of interactions stand out. They also noted that students show increased fear, anxiety, or sadness, as well as constant worry, discouragement, and lack of concentration. These emotions are often linked to low self-esteem and reduced participation in school activities. For example: "Discouragement in classroom activities. The student appears insecure when interacting with classmates. Withdraws from peers. Is afraid to attend classes" (F10).

Another group of teachers associated GBV with a decline in academic performance, evidenced by lower grades, reduced participation, or difficulties with concentration: "When the student changes their personal behavior, when they have low grades" (M8).

Likewise, a significant group of teachers identified difficulties in working in mixed-gender groups, situations of discrimination or exclusion, or the reproduction of stereotypical gender roles among students: "When she refuses to work with boys or when she has to carry out actions that are generally performed by males" (F9). To a lesser extent, they mentioned physical signs such as blows, bruises, or significant bodily changes: "Worried, weight loss, does not feel like talking to anyone, shy" (F8).

After the intervention, teachers provided more precise responses and incorporated a greater number of GBV indicators. They also demonstrated a clearer understanding of GBV dynamics, aligned with the workshop content: "I am confident in identifying whether a student is a victim of gender-based violence. Signs that make it evident: shyness when participating, this violence may be expressed in their drawings, fear of the opposite sex, acceptance of machista behaviors" (F15).

“I feel capable of listening to and identifying signs of violence, as well as acting immediately: low academic performance, shyness, limited interaction with boys in the case of girls (and vice versa), and fear of speaking.”

QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Knowledge of school policies regarding cases of gender-based violence (GBV) and the actions that can be taken

Similarly, in general terms, prior to the intervention, teachers had partial and predominantly operational knowledge of how to act in cases of gender-based violence (GBV).

First, many respondents identify the recognition, detection, and assessment of the case as initial steps to understand the situations that gave rise to the act of violence: “One of the first actions is to understand the situations that have led to the act of violence...” (M11).

Subsequently, most teachers indicated that communication and dialogue were fundamental actions, not only with the students involved—both victims and aggressors—but also with parents and caregivers. These actions included classroom dialogue, the drafting of incident reports, convening families, reporting the case to the tutoring area, and registering it in the corresponding system, as reflected in the following testimony: “In the classroom, dialogue is held with students and an incident report is prepared. Parents are invited to discuss what happened. The case is reported to the tutoring area. Uploaded to SiseVe” (F10).

Likewise, a significant number of teachers mentioned internal referrals to specialized areas within the educational institution, such as the Tutoring Committee, the Psychology Department, or school coexistence bodies: “We refer them, in the first instance, to the tutoring committee. If the case requires it, they are referred to the psychology area” (M10). In some cases, communication with school leadership was also noted when the problem persists, in order to ensure appropriate follow-up and the adoption of relevant measures: “First, talk with the students. Summon the parents. Communicate the problem to tutoring coordination. If the problem persists, discuss it and submit it to the management team” (F15)

To a lesser extent, teachers referred to more formal processes and official protocols related to responding to violence, such as registering cases on the Ministry of Education’s portal (SiseVe) or communicating with external institutions like the Women’s Emergency Center (CEM): “The policies are those related to violence protocols according to tutoring and SiseVe” (M12).

After the intervention, greater clarity was observed in teachers’ knowledge regarding school policies and the actions to be taken in cases of gender-based violence (GBV).

Unlike the initial responses, a more structured understanding of institutional procedures was evident, along with clear recognition of the official protocols of the Ministry of Education that must be followed—especially the use of the SiseVe platform as a formal mechanism for reporting and registering cases: “Yes, because now we know the six support protocols” (M8), and “1. Record the case in writing, exactly as the student reports it. 2. Report it to the School Coexistence Committee. 3. The coexistence committee must report it to SiseVe. 4. Follow up on the case” (F17).

Likewise, dialogue with the student and the family remained a key action, but it is now integrated into a defined institutional referral pathway that includes tutoring, psychology, specialized committees, and school leadership: “One of the first actions is to understand the situations that gave rise to the act of violence. Then, it is referred to the appropriate office to follow up on the case. Finally, measures are taken and the relevant institutions in charge are informed” (M11).

CONCLUSIONS

The results show that, prior to the intervention, most teachers already had predominantly favorable attitudes toward gender equality. They also demonstrated an initial understanding, mainly based on observation and classroom experience, of some signs of violence in the school environment, as well as the actions to follow in such situations.

However, this knowledge was often partial and mainly operational, with gaps in conceptual clarity and the handling of official protocols.

After the intervention, a significant strengthening of teachers' capacities is observed, reflected in greater confidence in identifying cases of gender-based violence, a more precise understanding of its manifestations, and a more structured grasp of the existing official and institutional referral pathways and protocols.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1

Strengthen continuous professional development for teachers

It is recommended to continue investing in periodic training interventions aimed at teaching staff, in order to consolidate understanding of gender-based violence (GBV), strengthen the early identification of signs, and deepen the implementation of institutional and Ministry of Education protocols.

2

Consolidate the understanding of gender in pedagogical practice

It is recommended to strengthen the practical application of the learning acquired in the classroom. This entails promoting pedagogical strategies that challenge gender stereotypes across different subjects.

3

Systematically incorporate reflection on gender stereotypes and new masculinities

Based on the identification of explicit and subtle manifestations of hegemonic masculinity, it is recommended to further deepen pedagogical work on gender stereotypes and new masculinities, promoting spaces for reflection with students that make visible power relations, peer violence, and the structural barriers that particularly affect women.

4

Reinforce knowledge and effective use of the GBV response pathways

It is recommended to periodically reinforce training on the referral pathway for responding to school violence arising from gender-based violence (GBV), as established by MINEDU, with emphasis on the correct application of the protocols set out in Annex No. 3 of Supreme Decree 004-2018-MINEDU and the mandatory use of the SiseVe platform as the formal mechanism for case registration and reporting.

RECOMMENDATIONS

5

Adopt an integrated approach involving the entire educational community

It is essential to address gender-based violence (GBV) through a comprehensive approach that articulates the involvement of the different actors within the educational community: students, teachers, and parents/caregivers. The active participation of these actors is key to prevention, early detection, and the construction of safe, violence-free school environments.

6

Strengthen inter-institutional coordination for GBV case management

It is recommended to promote more active coordination between the educational institution and external support and protection services, such as the Women's Emergency Centers (CEM), Línea 100, and other state agencies, in order to ensure comprehensive and timely attention to cases of gender-based violence (GBV).

7

Mainstream gender, human rights, and interculturality in pedagogical and institutional management

Strengthen the mainstreaming of gender, human rights, and interculturality approaches within institutional management instruments and pedagogical practice, promoting preventive and educational actions aimed at students, teachers, and families.

REFERENCES

Archdeacon, N., Salmon-Mulanovich, G., Lopez Florez, L., Kothadia, A., Castañeda, K., Rusyidi, B., ... Tallman, P. (2024). Teenage pregnancy in Tambogrande, Peru: causes, consequences, and cycles of violence and disadvantage. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 26(4), 563–574. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691058.2023.2193250>

